

Projection spread caused by missing in PCA on modern Eurasian populations:
 Approx. # non-missing SNPs = 18000

Approx Geographical location

- a Caucasus
- a Middle_East
- a North_Europe
- a SouthEast_Asia
- a Uralic
- a East_Asia
- a North_Asia
- a South_Asia
- a SouthEur